

Time-Independent Equation of Wave-Function with the Viewpoint of Relativity

The wave function, a cornerstone of quantum mechanics developed in the early 20th century, stands as a pivotal concept in understanding the behavior of particles at the atomic and subatomic levels. In contrast to classical mechanics, where particles adhere to well-defined trajectories, quantum mechanics relies on the wave function to convey the probabilistic nature inherent in these particles. Symbolised by the Greek letter Ψ (psi), the wave function serves as a mathematical representation that hinges on the coordinates of a particle – including its position and momentum. The square of this wave function, $|\Psi|^2$, serves to provide the probability density of locating the particle at any given point. At the heart of quantum mechanics lies the Schrödinger equation, a fundamental equation dictating the evolution of the wave function over time. This partial differential equation establishes a link between the energy of a system and its corresponding wave function. By solving the Schrödinger equation, scientists can discern potential energy levels and their associated wave functions for a specific quantum system. A notable characteristic of quantum mechanics is the wave-particle duality, emphasising the dual nature of particles as both waves and particles. This concept becomes tangible through the notion of wave packets, which represent localised clusters of waves corresponding to the particle's position. Werner Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, a foundational tenet of quantum mechanics, asserts that certain pairs of properties – such as position and momentum – cannot be precisely known simultaneously. This principle, arising from the wave nature of particles, carries profound implications for our comprehension of the microscopic realm. Quantum superposition, a key quantum mechanical concept, allows particles to exist in multiple states concurrently until a measurement collapses the wave function, yielding a specific outcome. This idea is vividly illustrated in the well-known thought experiment called Schrödinger's cat. Quantum entanglement, another noteworthy quantum phenomenon, occurs when particles become correlated in such a manner that the state of one particle instantaneously influences the state of another, regardless of the physical distance between them. These entangled particles share a joint wave function, and changes to one particle's state instantaneously affect the other. Despite the success of quantum mechanics in elucidating microscopic phenomena, the interpretation of the wave function remains a subject of ongoing debate. Various interpretations, including the Copenhagen interpretation, the many-worlds interpretation, and de Broglie-Bohm theory, offer distinct perspectives on the nature of reality and the role of the wave function in describing it. In summary, the wave function serves as a pivotal concept in quantum mechanics, providing a mathematical depiction of the probabilistic nature of particles. It plays a crucial role in comprehending particle behaviour at the quantum level, encompassing concepts such as wave-particle duality, quantum superposition, and quantum entanglement. The wave function and its associated principles have revolutionised our understanding of the microscopic world, challenging classical intuitions and paving the way for technological advancements in areas such as quantum computing and quantum communication. Before delving into the main topic, let us discuss about the mass-energy equivalency (special relativity). Mass-energy equivalence is a fundamental concept in physics, famously expressed by Albert Einstein through his iconic equation, $E=mc^2$. This equation, where E represents energy, m denotes mass, and c is the speed of light in a vacuum, has profound implications for our understanding of the interconversion between mass and energy. Einstein's ground-breaking insight emerged during the early 20th century, a period marked by significant advancements in theoretical physics. At the time, the prevailing view considered mass and energy as distinct entities with separate conservation principles. However, Einstein's revolutionary idea challenged this dichotomy, asserting that mass and energy were interchangeable in certain circumstances. To comprehend mass-energy equivalence, it is crucial to delve into the implications of Einstein's equation. The speed of light, denoted by ' c ,' is an enormous constant – approximately 3×10^8 meters per second. This means that the conversion factor between mass and energy is substantial. Consequently, even a small amount of mass can be converted into a vast amount of energy, and vice versa. The essence of mass-energy equivalence can be illustrated through practical examples, such as

nuclear reactions. In nuclear processes, a minute quantity of mass is transformed into a considerable amount of energy. The most iconic illustration of this principle is the energy released in nuclear fission and fusion reactions. The mass defect, representing the difference between the mass of the reactants and the mass of the products, is converted into energy according to $E=mc^2$. Consider the atomic bomb, where a small amount of mass is converted into an immense release of energy. The destructive power of atomic weapons is a stark demonstration of the potential energy stored within the nucleus of atoms. This phenomenon highlights the importance of understanding mass-energy equivalence not only from a theoretical perspective but also in practical applications. Moreover, mass-energy equivalence has far-reaching consequences in astrophysics. In the core of stars, including our sun, nuclear fusion reactions occur, converting hydrogen nuclei into helium and releasing energy in the process. This energy, emanating from the conversion of mass, is what sustains the luminosity and heat emitted by stars. The concept of mass-energy equivalence thus plays a central role in elucidating the energy production mechanisms that govern the life cycle of stars. Additionally, the fusion reactions occurring within stars also produce heavier elements through nucleosynthesis. This process, essential for the creation of elements beyond helium, is a testament to the intricate interplay between mass and energy on a cosmic scale. The elements forged in stars are the building blocks of planets, including Earth, and all the matter in the universe. In the realm of particle physics, mass-energy equivalence is fundamental to understanding the behavior of subatomic particles. Particle accelerators, such as the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), accelerate particles to velocities approaching the speed of light, resulting in significant relativistic effects. In these experiments, the conversion between mass and energy becomes evident as particles gain energy and mass relativistically. The practical application of mass-energy equivalence extends beyond the confines of physics laboratories and astronomical observations. Medical technologies, such as positron emission tomography (PET) scans, leverage the principles of mass-energy equivalence. In PET scans, positron-emitting radionuclides are used to detect and visualize metabolic processes in the human body. The annihilation of positrons with electrons produces gamma rays, and the resulting energy release is precisely measured to create detailed images of internal biological activities. While mass-energy equivalence has found widespread application in various scientific disciplines, it also raises philosophical questions about the nature of matter and energy. The idea that mass can be converted into energy challenges our intuitive understanding of the physical world. It prompts us to reevaluate the fundamental nature of the entities that constitute the fabric of the universe. In conclusion, mass-energy equivalence, encapsulated in Einstein's $E=mc^2$, stands as one of the cornerstones of modern physics. Its far-reaching implications extend from the microscopic world of particle physics to the grand scale of astrophysics. Understanding the interconversion between mass and energy has not only revolutionized our theoretical frameworks but has also paved the way for ground-breaking technological applications, transforming the way we perceive and interact with the physical universe.

Therefore, we know the full form of mass-energy equivalency as,

$$E^2 = m^2c^4 + p^2c^2 \quad (1)$$

However, let us consider the simple form of the equation,

$$E = \gamma mc^2$$

Let us consider 'm' as the mass of an electron and 'E' as the total energy. We can write,

$$E = (\gamma mc^2 - mc^2) + mc^2 \quad (2)$$

$$= \left(\frac{\gamma m^2 v^2 c^2}{m v^2} - mc^2 \right) + mc^2$$

$$= \left(\frac{\gamma p^2 c^2}{m v^2} - mc^2 \right) + mc^2 \quad (3)$$

Again,

$$\Psi = e^{i(kx-wt)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Rightarrow \frac{d\Psi}{dx} &= ik e^{i(kx-wt)} = ik\Psi \\
\Rightarrow \frac{d^2\Psi}{d^2x} &= (ik)^2\Psi = -\left(\frac{p^2}{\hbar^2}\right)\Psi \\
\Rightarrow -\hbar^2 \frac{d^2\Psi}{d^2x} &= p^2\Psi
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Multiplying the equation no.3 with Ψ we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned}
E\Psi &= \left(\frac{\gamma p^2 c^2}{mv^2}\Psi - mc^2\Psi\right) + mc^2\Psi \\
&= -\frac{\gamma\hbar c^2}{mv^2} \frac{d^2\Psi}{d^2x} - mc^2\Psi + mc^2\Psi
\end{aligned} \tag{Put the value of } p^2\Psi$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E\Psi &= -\frac{\gamma\hbar c^2}{mv^2} \frac{d^2\Psi}{d^2x} - mc^2\Psi + mc^2\Psi \\
&\quad \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_a \qquad \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_b \\
&\quad \text{Kinetic energy} \qquad \text{Potential energy}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Here,

m = Mass of the electron;

v = Velocity of the electron;

c = Speed of light;

$\hbar$ = Planck's reduced constant;

γ = Lorentz's factor.

$$\begin{aligned}
M\Psi &= -\frac{\gamma\hbar}{mv^2} \frac{d^2\Psi}{d^2x} - m\Psi + m\Psi \\
\text{Total mass} &\quad \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_a \qquad \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_b \\
&\quad \text{The mass that increases} \qquad \text{Mass in rest} \\
&\quad \text{due to motion}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

In relativity, mass and energy are considered equivalent. Thus, we express this by factoring out c^2 from the left side and dividing the right side by it. Subsequently, we represent energy as 'M' instead of E/c^2 , resulting in equation no.6. This allows us to elucidate the wave-function using mass, implying the inability to pinpoint the electron mass in a specific position within an atom. The atom harbors a distributed intensity of mass, enabling the calculation of the probability of the electron's position. Notably, if mass and energy differ, the electron's energy could exist as a cloud in the atom, with varying intensity at different points. However, the electron's mass is confined to a specific location. It's crucial to recognize that the presented equation is limited to a single dimension, and its accuracy awaits validation through practical experiments. We also assert that we have formulated the relativity equation as $E = KE + PE$, culminating in result equation no.2.

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